

Of Rival

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Abstract: There are two types of friends. They are class friend and glass friend. Class friend may be rival but seldom the glass friend. The glass friends meet in the bar but their relation faces no bar. Glass is brittle. But the relation is rigid. They drink wine. They drink life to the lees. They know that life is only for once. They have the secret password for happiness. They are whisked away from the hard reality. As such they know how to enjoy life thereby conquer rivalry.

Keywords: Rival, rivalry, competition, equal, comparable, enemy

INTRODUCTION

Creative writing is based more on manifestation rather than on expression. It does not inform, rather it reveals. So it bears no reference. The best creative writing is critical, and the best critical writing is creative. This article is an outcome of thinking about creative writing meant for a general readership. As such, I have adopted a free style methodology so that everyone can enjoy the pleasure of reading. As you might know, Francis Bacon (1561-1626), the immortal essayist, wrote many essays namely 'Of Love', 'Of Friendship', 'Of Ambition', 'Of Studies', and so on. The multiple-minded genius correctly pointed out that all the words of the dictionary can be used as themes for essays. But little has been done since his death to continue or finish his monumental task. Bacon's unique individual style of presentation ignited my imagination and encouraged me to write creative essays as a method of relieving a wide range of emotions through catharsis.

ARTICLE

Rival is a person or thing competing with another for the same objective or for superiority in the same field of activity. For example: He has no serious rival for the job.

It is be or seem to be equal or comparable to. For example: He was a photographer whose fame rivalled that of his subjects.

It is to be as good, clever, beautiful, etc. as someone or something else. For example: No computer can rival a human brain for/in complexity. The beauty of the country is only rivalled by (= is as great in degree as) the violence of its politics.

Rival is a negative term. It is derogatory in nature. It endangers life. It destroys relation. It vitiates the emotion. It provokes to do harm to the opponent. Sometimes it comes back as boomerang. As such a wise avoids it. In contrast, a fool uses it and be involved in this dirty game intentionally.

Man faces rivalry. He has to face it. He is bound to face it. Thus man, willy-nilly, faces rivalry infinite times from cradle to coffin in its various forms and features having different degrees and dimensions as well.

Sometimes he is liable. Sometimes he is not. Thus he is both the cause and because of rivalry simultaneously. The paradox is that someone wants to avoid rivalry honestly but rivalry does not want to leave him at all. Only a judicious person can tackle rivalry tactfully seldom a fool. Very few persons know this tact. More few apply this tact effectively. It is really an art. All are not artists. All cannot be artists. All are not destined to be artists. This answers why most of the persons be involved in rivalry either willingly or unwillingly or both simultaneously.

Rich or poor, high birth or low birth, educated or uneducated, cultured or uncultured, enlightened or dark continent, haves or have-nots, bourgeois or proletariat i.e., people from all walks of life face rivalry. All are equal and at par to rivalry. In this regard rivalry is quite democratic in its nature and behaviour. It levels all and everybody with its violent force. As such everybody surrenders to rivalry unconditionally.

Exposure of rivalry varies from person to person. Also it depends on education and socio-economic status of the concerned person as well. The exposure of uncultured person is rough and that of cultured person is sophisticated in nature.

Rivalry is the only thing which grows automatically without any care just like jungle trees. It disturbs the intimacy. It creates distance. It poisons the environment. It is just like ill weeds grow apace. Care sharpens it. A fool nurtures it. A wise hates it. The learned considers rivalry as merely wastage of time and energy as well.

Rivalry cannot be destroyed, rather it destroys the relation. It closes all the doors of communication. It is too easy to close a door, but too difficult to reopen it. As such a judicious person seldom closes the doors of intimacy with others. None knows who will be the only Good Samaritan in danger. The Samaritan may be the opponent person. Sometimes an enemy may appear as the rescuer even.

A lay man destroys relation callously. He does not get help in danger. An intelligent person values man more than money. Money cannot solve all the problems of life as are faced with. All are not commodities. So all and everybody cannot be purchased. Money has its limitation. Very few persons know it. Power and probability of relation are unlimited. They help. They pave the way to survive.

Rivalry may be manifested either silently or violently. A shrewd person operates it silently. In contrast the operation of a fool is crude in nature. He lacks in talent, tact and temperament as well. As such his outcome is violent. He is exposed to all and everybody. So he is blamed easily. In contrast an intelligent

person cannot be identified for this action. The protagonist always remains unknown everywhere in every age.

Rivalry among two nations is called cold war. Two intellectuals also prefer and practise cold war. It is used as a tool of politics. They say politics means polite and tricks or poly tricks. The ultimate or ultimatum of cold war is nuclear war. Modern world suffers from this imminent danger. This danger may be virtual or actual. Civilisation is suffering from this genuine phobia of rivalry. Enemy is rival. It does not amaze us. It hurts when a friend is rival or a brother is rival over property. Similarly, father may be rival even if both father and son come into the same profession.

There are two types of friends. They are class friend and glass friend. Class friend may be rival but seldom the glass friend. The glass friends meet in the bar but their relation faces no bar. Glass is brittle. But the relation is rigid. They drink wine. They drink life to the lees. They know that life is only for once. They have the secret password for happiness. They are whisked away from the hard reality. As such they know how to enjoy life thereby conquer rivalry.

They are guided by emotion rather than motion. Motion is mundane. Emotion is divine. Motion faces rivalry. Emotion experiences welcome. Motion divides. Emotion unites. Here lies the overriding effect of emotion over motion. The paradox is that emotion is valued less in reality. Emotion breaks all barriers and crosses all boundaries with its tender force but uncontrollable in nature.

A class friend becomes rival with his dear class mate for contesting the single assignment. He is guided by motion. He wants to reach his desired goal by any means fair or foul. He leaves no stone unturned to realize his ambition.

A rival should be handled very carefully. Two fools quarrel. Two wise never quarrel. A fool murders its rival and is caught red-handed for its callousness. A wise attacks with logic. A lay man wants to win through magic.

Rival is alias and akin to envy that gives birth to conflict which culminates to bloodshed even.

A judicious person keeps safe distance from the object or objective that causes and creates trouble. He leaves the matter of dispute that creates competition. He intends to overcome the distance that has been generated automatically. He contends that there is good, there is better, there is best and there is better than best even. So a chance may be replaced by another better one. This positive essence is a great driving force. It conveys the message of optimism that escorts a better destination. There is no rival. The atmosphere is so peaceful. Peace is his single agenda. He can leave everything for peace but he is not ready to leave peace for anything. He possesses wide heart.

Competition is too good. Unhealthy competition is too bad. There are two types of persons. The first category likes competition. He welcomes competition. The second category avoids competition. He competes with himself. He himself is his rival. He competes with his yesterday's output for better outcome. Time is his true rival. He competes with time. He knows time and tide wait for none. He moves ahead with this unique and innovative strategy. He advances towards his target silently quite unaware of others. His sudden rise and success bewilder all and everybody around him.

For a single post if the competitors are many rivals are many accordingly. It is generally seen in case of unskilled labourers where the population is illiterate. If the vacancies are many and applicants are less then rivalry is absent. It is true in case of specialised job. Only an expert can do that job with his unique expertise. There are many vacancies for experts. But experts are numbered. The present world is suffering from this vacuum.

Technology is changing vary rapidly. Updation of knowledge is a must. Very few persons can do that. As such today's expert simply becomes a scrap tomorrow for lacking in latest

knowledge. As such knowledge is the greatest enemy of the knowledgeable expert.

Ordinary job can easily be done by ordinary people. Extraordinary work can only be done by a person having extraordinary merit. Specialised job needs and demands talent and perseverance. Very few persons have that capacity. Thinking is alias and akin to physical pain. Very few persons can bear that pain to gain expertise. This answers why we notice so many imperfect persons around us.

Imperfect persons cannot do anything with their imperfect or part or half knowledge. They say a little learning is a dangerous thing. As such a half genius is dangerous more than a non-genius.

If two rivals are fool then there is danger in every footstep. If the rivals are intelligent then the danger is more. The danger may either be in sophisticated manner or violent in nature or both simultaneously. The rivals may be genius. They may be diverted. Then such a diverted genius may be a misguided missile. Such a misguided missile is either dangerously brilliant or brilliantly dangerous or both simultaneously. Then their mood and motive become violent.

CONCLUSION

Rivalry may be temporary or permanent. Sometimes temporary rivalry may be converted into permanent rivalry or permanent rivalry may be converted into a temporary one. So its locus standee is difficult to ascertain.

REFERENCES

No reference, since the present article is an outcome of Creative Nonfiction Writing.